

USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article discusses the usage and effectiveness of authentic materials in teaching English. Authentic materials can be used to increase learners’ interest, and engage classes that meet students’ learning objectives. The richness of language found in authentic materials provides the resources learners need for language acquisition.

Key words: authentic materials, language teaching, learners.

What do we mean by authentic materials?

According to the new objectives, the task of the foreign language teacher is to create the conditions for the familiarization of the student's personality with the foreign language culture and to prepare them for effective participation in the cultural dialogue. Therefore, in foreign language teaching, a special emphasis is placed on forms of involvement using authentic materials that ensure the active participation of each student in the lesson, stimulate oral communication, and contribute to the formation of interest and desire to learn a foreign language.

In recent years, much attention has been paid to the issue of authenticity in foreign language teaching methodology and the term “authentic materials” has been started to use replacing the term “original material” in modern domestic and foreign methods. The “authentic materials” mean the learning content taken from genuine sources such as news, outlets, podcasts, video sharing platforms, and texts that were written by native speakers and published specifically for native-speaker consumption. Teachers can easily create questions, activities, or projects around authentic materials that match students’ levels and relate to personal or professional interests and goals.

Why choose authentic materials?

Coursebooks can be useful resources for both teachers and learners for English lessons, that determine the components and methods of learning. Most coursebooks are accompanied by a teacher's guide that provides supplementary materials, ideas, and activities for use throughout the academic year. But sometimes they may be outdated or cover a subject area insufficiently. Texts presented for reading in the book may not correspond to the student's level of knowledge. Texts, dialogs, and other aspects of the content are usually written specifically to incorporate teaching points and often do not represent authentic language. They do not always reflect students' interests and needs, as they are written for the global market.

Choosing the best content of authentic materials depends on the learner, their level of English, and the course content the teacher wants to focus on. Authentic materials provide examples of language used in everyday situations and information about the target culture and its perspective on a topic or event. Authentic texts are defined as “written by members of a language and culture group for members of the same language and culture group” (Galloway, 1998, p. 133, as cited in Glisan). Sharing and working with real texts, videos, and listening materials often motivates students. Eventually, they realize they can truly understand real-world texts (rather than coursebook materials).

Authentic texts taken from periodicals are up-to-date and topical having reason to be read with interest. Students not only practice their English, but they can update their knowledge on specific area. For instance, students who are learning Business English, will become experts in reading English texts, and other business publications also by practicing reading *The Economist* at the English lessons.

Authentic teaching materials can be used to supplement the structure and vocabulary presented in your syllabus and textbooks, and enhance synergistic learning. Such materials include articles and other literature, videos, podcasts, songs, menus, etc. that address topic already covered in textbooks. Materials should reflect the situations learners will face in an English-speaking environment. This helps learners transition to a world where English is the norm. In the English-speaking world, people use abbreviations, body language, and "fillers" like "hmm" which are

all important for comprehension and learners encounter these in authentic teaching materials. Suppose a textbook covers the topic of food and restaurants, and presents food language and ordering grammar. It is easy to find a wealth of material on the Internet in varying degrees of difficulty, including restaurant menus, articles about restaurant cuisine, and restaurant reviews... These materials can then be used in a variety of ways.

References:

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